

seems to have been done on the stem bark of this plant. In view of this fact and its high medicinal utility, a chemical investigation of bark of this plant has been undertaken in this laboratory.

Experimental

Air dried powdered bark of the plant (collected from Baliguni, Nanoor, District Birbhum, W. Bengal) was successively extracted with petroleum ether (60-80°) and benzene. Petroleum ether extract was chromatographed over Brockmann alumina. Elution with benzene provided a gummy material which on repeated chromatographies over neutral alumina and silica-gel yielded a white solid m.p. 135°-136°. It gave positive Libermann-Burchardt test and was identified as β -sitosterol by m. m.p. determination; Co-TLC with authentic sample of β -sitosterol and the preparation of its acetate m. p. 127°-28°.

The benzene extract on chromatography over Brockmann alumina and on elution with petroleum ether (60-80°) furnished a white crystalline solid m.p. 258°-59° which responds to positive Libermann-Burchardt test for triterpenes. It forms a D.N.P.H. derivative, m.p. 293°-94° (dec). It was identified as friedelin by m.m.p. determination; Co-TLC and Co-IR with authentic specimen of the compound.

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Chemical Examination of the Roots of *Stereospermum suaveolens* DC.

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STEREOSPERMUM *suaveolens* DC. (Bignoniaceae) is distributed throughout India and is reported to have medicinal importance¹. Its different

parts are indigenously used as local remedies for different diseases. The root bark forms an ingredient in dasamula, an Indian preparation used as tonic. Flowers are taken in the form of a confection as an aphrodis. No work seems to have been done on the roots of this plant and hence a systematic study of this part was undertaken. We have obtained lapachol, dehydro- α -lapachone, dehydrotectol and β -sitosterol from the heartwood and β -sitosterol and n-triacontanol from the bark.

Root heartwood: Dried and powdered root heartwood was thoroughly extracted with pet. ether (60-80°). The concentrated extract was taken in ether and extracted with 2N-sodium carbonate and separated into acidic and neutral fractions.

Acidic fraction:

Lapachol: The acidic fraction was chromatographed over silica gel. Elution with petroleum ether=benzene (2:3) afforded lapachol², a yellow compound, m.p. 139-40° (pet. ether); $C_{15}H_{14}O_8$; IR, ν_{max}^{KBr} : 3330 cm^{-1} (O-H stretch), 1660 cm^{-1} and 1640 cm^{-1} (C=O stretch of the quinonoid system). It gave red colouration with alcoholic magnesium acetate and aqueous NaOH.

Neutral fraction:

This was chromatographed over deactivated alumina whereupon the following compounds were obtained.

Dehydrotectol: Elution of the column with petroleum ether yielded dark blue crystals of dehydrotectol³, m.p. 192-3° (MeOH); $C_{29}H_{54}O_4$; I. R., ν_{max}^{KBr} : 1645 cm^{-1} (C=O stretch), identical (mmp, TLC and IR) with an authentic sample. It gave tectol on refluxing with zinc dust.

Dehydro- α -lapachone: Elution of the column with petroleum ether-benzene (4:1) gave orange needles of dehydro- α -lapachone⁴, m.p. 142-3° (pet. ether); $C_{15}H_{12}O_8$; IR, ν_{max}^{KBr} : 1680 cm^{-1} , 1640 cm^{-1} (C=O stretch of the quinonoid system), 705 cm^{-1} (aromatic C-H deformation); identical (mmp, TLC and IR) with an authentic specimen.

β -Sitosterol: Further elution of the column with petroleum ether-benzene (1:1) furnished β -sitosterol; m.p. 136-8° (EtOH); $C_{29}H_{50}O$; acetate (Ac₂O/pyr.) m.p. 126-8°.

Root bark: The finely ground root bark was extracted with petroleum ether and the concentrated extract was chromatographed over deactivated alumina.

β -Sitosterol: Elution of the column with petroleum ether gave β -sitosterol, m.p. 137-8°, identical (mmp, IR and TLC) with an authentic specimen.

A lignan: Further elution with petroleum ether

gave a pale yellow compound, m.p. 140-1° (CHCl₃ : pet. ether); $\nu_{\text{Nujol}}^{\text{max}}$: 1710 cm⁻¹, 1660 cm⁻¹, 1610 cm⁻¹ and 1580 cm⁻¹. It gave an intense red colour with conc. H₂SO₄ and a dark blue-green spot on TLC (spray reagent 2% ceric sulphate in 2N H₂SO₄). These results indicate that the compound is probably a lignan. Further structural studies are still in progress.

n-Triacontanol: Elution of the column with petroleum ether-benzene (4 : 1) gave n-triacontanol⁶, m.p. 83-4° (EtOAc); C₃₀H₆₂O; IR, $\nu_{\text{Nujol}}^{\text{max}}$: 3110 cm⁻¹ (H-bonded O-H stretch), 1020 cm⁻¹ (C-O stretch), 730 and 720 cm⁻¹ [(—CH₂—)_n, n > 4, bending]; acetate (Ac₂O/pyr.) m.p. 66-7°.

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Chemical Constituents of the Roots of *Dichrostachys cinerea* Macb. and the Stembark and Heartwood of *Acacia leucophloea* Willd.

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DICHRSTOCHYS *cinerea* and *Acacia leucophloea* both belong to the family Leguminosae. The roots of *D. cinerea* are astringent and used in rheumatism and renal troubles¹. The stembark, heartwood and leaves of *D. cinerea* have been examined earlier.² The flowers of *A. leucophloea* contain glucoside of myricetin³. This note reports the results of chemical examination of the roots of *D. cinerea* and stembark and heartwood of *A. leucophloea*.

Examination of the roots of *Dichrostachys cinerea* Macb :

The coarsely powdered roots on benzene extraction yielded a semisolid mass which on chromatography over deactivated alumina yielded the following compounds :

n-Octacosanol: Elution of the column with petroleum-ether (60-80°) afforded crystalline n-octacosanol, m.p. 83-84°, acetate, m.p. 64-65°, identified (mmp, TLC and IR) with an authentic sample.

β-Amyrin: Further elution of the column with petroleum-ether (60-80°) furnished β-amyrin, m.p. 198-199°. It was identified on the basis of IR, m.m.p. and by preparing its acetate, m.p. 238°.

Friedelan 3-one: Elution of the column with petroleum ether-benzene (9 : 1) yielded friedelan-3-one, m.p. 260° and was confirmed by reduction (NaBH₄) to friedelan-3β-ol, C₃₀H₅₂O, m.p. 276-278° (m.m.p. TLC and IR.)

Friedelan-3β-ol: Further elution of the original column with petroleum-ether and benzene (9 : 1) afforded friedelan-3β-ol, m.p. 278°, identical (mmp, TLC and IR) with an authentic specimen. On acetylation it gave an acetate, m.p. 290-291°.

β-Sitosterol: Elution of the column with petroleum ether-benzene (1 : 1) furnished β-sitosterol, m.p. 136-137°, acetate, m.p. 126-127°.

Examination of the Stembark of *A. leucophloea* Willd :

The benzene extract of the stembark on chromatography over deactivated alumina yielded the following compounds :

n-Hexacosanol: Elution with petroleum-ether (60-80°) afforded colourless n-hexacosanol, m.p. 79-80°, acetate, m.p. 64-65°.

β-Sitosterol: Further elution of the column with petroleum-ether-benzene (4 : 1) yielded β-sitosterol, m.p. 136-137°.

β-Amyrin: Elution of the column with petroleum ether-benzene (1 : 1) afforded β-amyrin, m.p. 198° identical (mmp, TLC and IR) with an authentic specimen. On acetylation it gave an acetate, m.p. 238°.

Examination of the heartwood of *A. leucophloea* Willd :

The petroleum ether (60-80°) extract of the dried and coarsely powdered heartwood on chromatography over deactivated alumina yielded the follow-